

The Different Impact between Transformational Leadership and Transactional Leadership on Competitive Advantage

¹Devie, ²Hatane Samuel, ³Hotlan Siagian

¹Department of Accounting, Petra Christian University, Surabaya, Indonesia.

²Department of Magister Management, Petra Christian University, Surabaya, Indonesia.

³Department of Magister Management, Petra Christian University, Surabaya, Indonesia.

Abstract

The objective of this research is to investigate the influence of leadership styles towards developing company's competitive advantages. This research is doing for some sectors of companies in Surabaya of Indonesia, i.e. manufacturing, service, retail, financial service, distributor, and property sectors. Furthermore, this research investigates the difference results of the model among those sectors. There are 82 companies as the research objects in and the unit analysis. Each company consist of five respondents, which is in totals are 410 respondents, those are managers, supervisors, and staffs. They answer the questionnaire as the tool in this research. This research finds that compares to transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style has more influence in developing the competitive advantage of companies in Surabaya. Intellectual stimulation is the characteristic of transformational leadership style that highly influencing the development of competitive advantage. While giving commends to employees that have extraordinary performance is the dominant characteristic of transactional leadership style in the research model. The ways the leadership styles use in developing their competitive advantages also different each other. Transformational leadership more focus on quality-product innovation; transactional leadership more focus on delivery dependability and time to market.

Keyword: Leadership Style; Transformational leadership; Transactional leadership; Competitive Advantage.

Background

Globalization and change is two key important word to win the competition. There are many changing factors which are caused by globalization so that the company can compete [1]. In the era of globalization, rapid change is not enough, the presence of advanced technology systems, understanding complexity of customer needs, and the invention of unique products is also important. Indonesian as emerging countries have to change to compete in the globalization era. [2] said that Indonesian Competitiveness was not maximized yet. There are three indicators; namely prosperity growth rates have only been average relative to regional peers, limited integration into the global economy, and significant competitiveness weaknesses. Based on [2] view about Indonesian Competitiveness, Indonesian entrepreneurial leaders have to improve competitive capability to increase organization performance which automatically will boost Indonesian's prosperity. Customer takes control in the globalization era. Organization needs market orientation to compete against one another in the worldwide global market [3].

Leadership is the back bone of an organization [4]. Effective and capable Leaders are expected to inspire employee to face continuously creativity and relationship as needed in global market. Effective leadership will continually and progressively leading and directing followers to focus on the objective of organization. Not all managers are leaders and, equally, not all leaders are managers [4], so organization need a leader a not manager. There are many leadership styles which could be applied in an organization. According to theory and acts of leadership, there are two major style which are Transformational Leadership and Transactional Leadership [5]. Transformational leadership is one of the leadership style that has been found to be preferred by employees [6], but transactional leadership also influence for employee performance through pushes the followers to do the works as what the leaders expect to get reward and promotion [7]. Leadership will brings a tremendous impact in achieving competitive advantage [8].

This empirical study is conducted to explore the impact of leadership style on the competitive capabilities and then to investigate the different impact between Transformational Leadership and transactional leadership on the competitive advantage.

Literature Review

Competitive Advantage

Achieving competitive advantage is the main goal of companies [9]. Every organization wants to lead the market. To achieve market Leader position, organization must have competitive advantage to compete with the competitors. [10] said that flexibility and response time for consumers' needs is the an essential factor for a company create competitive advantage. Competitive advantage is about choosing the proper strategy which is suitable to the company's resources as the requirement to be successful in market place [11, 12]defined Competitive Capabilities in five dimensions, namely: Pricing/Cost, Quality, Dependable Delivery, Product Innovation, and time to market. [13] said that Competitive advantage is created when a company has an ability to produce a product with lower budget compared to its competitor's product. The ability of an organization to offer quality and performance of a product which can give additional value to the customers [14]. Dependable Delivery is capable of competing with the competitor to offer the fulfillment of delivery requirement. Product Innovation is capable of competing with the competitor to offer new products and features in market place. Innovations that lead to competitive advantage [14].

Leadership Style

Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership is one of leadership styles that fit to the changing in the market. There are four characteristic of Transformational Leadership: idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration [5].

Idealized Influence (also known as Charismatic Leadership). Transformational leaders is a visionary leader because they have a clear vision and willing to take risk. Transformation leader always sharpen the vision to target of organization performance. Transformational Leader is also a charismatic Leader because they are respected, admired and trusted. Transformational leader have a good value because they have high moral and ethical standards. To pursue organization performance, Transformational Leader always give a sign what can do and what can not do.

Inspirational Motivation. Transformational Leader is a motivator because they show enthusiasm and optimism, providing both meaning and challenge to the work at hand, and build dynamic team. They motivate people through share vision and goal commitment. Transformational Leaders always work together with and give directing employee to focus Organization Performance.

Intellectual Stimulation. Transformational Leader is a change agent because they encourages creativity and actively solicit new ideas and new ways of doing thing. Transformational Leader will support employee to Involve supplier and customer to collect new idea from them to create Competitive Advantage.

Individualized Consideration. Transformational leaders act as mentors and coaches because they always empower people to improve. They also recognize Individual desires and needs. Transformational Leader always integrate organization goal and individual goal so that employee eager to learn to achieve organization goal while to achieve personal goal.

Transactional Leadership

Besides that, transactional leaders can facilitate the subordinates to be closer to their obligations and the targets, thus the leaders can predicts the subordinates' level of performances. Job satisfaction, innovation skill, work efficiency, and performance improvement can be achieved in organizations that apply transactional leadership style. One characteristic of the style is focus on plan-control that consist of developing the standards, policies, procedures, regulations, and assume that each subordinate will be motivated by reward and punishment system.

Transactional leadership is exchange process between the leaders and the subordinates [15, 16, 17]. Leaders who have transactional leadership style point on the important of barter process between the needs of the subordinates and the needs of the ordinates (leaders). The leaders will full fill the subordinates' needs if they can achieve targets from their leaders. Transactional leaders accommodate their subordinates by giving contingent rewards, in the term of incentives, promotions, bonuses, etc. In addition, transactional leaders can encourage their subordinates to behave in positive ways which inline which the leaders' objectives in order to get the rewards [18, 19, 20].

In addition, transactional leaders can encourage their subordinates to behave in positive ways which inline which the leaders' objectives in order to get the rewards[7]. Besides that, transactional leaders can facilitate the subordinates to be closer to their obligations and the targets, thus the leaders can predicts the subordinates' level of performances[21].

Job satisfaction, innovation skill, work efficiency, and performance improvement can be achieved in organizations that apply transactional leadership style[22, 23]. One characteristic of the style is focus on plan-control that consist of developing the standards, policies, procedures, regulations, and assume that each subordinate will be motivated by reward and punishment system [24].

Leadership Style Influence on Competitive Advantage

Leadership is the main factor in the successfulness of the company. Therefore, it is important in organization management [25]. The successful company is the one that has competitive capability. The capability enables the company to win the completion, so leader become the determined factor in the process [8].

Leadership style is the combination of character and behavior of the leader that used in the Interaction with the subordinates, in order to direct and motivate them to be cooperative with the leader's objective or target [19, 26]. There are two popular leadership styles, transactional and transformational leadership styles [25, 27].

These leadership styles are convinced able to direct and motivate the subordinates in achieving organization's vision towards the creation of competitive advantage Leadership styles can inspire the subordinates in developing their best competencies to build organization's competitive advantages [8] The competitive advantage is the advantage that enable the organization to be different compares to its competitor [28] and success in market environment [11].

Transformational leader is a leadership that is ethical [29] and a charismatic person who inspires and encourages his followers to become more intelligent [4] and at the same time the leaders can improve the creativity of the employees [30]. Therefore, transformational leadership is the leadership style which enables the employees outside their own interest [31], thus it is convince that the followers will achieve better result compare to the leadership style [32].

Research Model and Hypothesis Development

Competitive Advantage is used as a dependent variable for this research. After defining and measuring the three variables, the researcher is interested in investigating the relationship between the two variables of performance drivers which cover Transformational Leadership and Transactional Leadership on Competitive Advantage. The model of three variables can be seen in the picture 1.

Picture 1. The Model of the Different Impact of Leadership Style on Competitive Advantage

Based on this model, this study is aimed at investigating the relationship between three latent variables, namely Competitive Advantage, Transactional Leadership, and Transformational Leadership. The relationship of this variable will derive 3 hypothesis based on the literature theory.

H1: The greater of Transformational Leadership, the greater its Competitive Capabilities

H2: The greater of Transactional Leadership, the greater its Competitive Capabilities

Research Methodology

Sample Size and Selection

The population in this research is all companies. Purposive random sampling has been applied for 82 companies. The samples are categorized in two groups, i.e. the dominant transactional leadership style group, and dominant transformational leadership style group. The grouping process used nine yes-no questions (indicators), which are 5 indicators for transformational leadership style, and 4 indicators for transactional. Table 1 gives information that there are 45 companies applied transformational leadership style, and 37 companies applied the transactional one.

Table 1. Data Respondent Based on Business Sector

business sector as a unit of analysis	the companies implement transformational leadership		the companies implement transactional leadership		total	
	count	percentage	count	percentage	count	percentage
manufacture	9	20.0%	10	27.0%	19	23.2%
service	19	42.2%	12	32.4%	31	37.8%
retail	3	6.7%	3	8.1%	6	7.3%
financial service	8	17.8%	2	5.4%	10	12.2%
distributor	6	13.3%	8	21.6%	14	17.1%
property	0	0.0%	2	5.4%	2	2.4%
Total	45	100.0%	37	100.0%	82	100.0%

From Table 1, the data description showed that the majority sector as the respondent is from service sector (37.8%), while from the property sector only about 2.4%. The composition of transformational leadership style in the service companies sector is 42.2%, which is the highest composition in all respondents.

The representatives of each company are 5 respondents who filled in the questionnaire. Total respondents in this research are 410 persons that spread in the level of managers, supervisors, and staffs. The respondents can be grouped in two groups, those are 225 respondents are working in the companies those have transformational leadership, and 185 respondents are working in companies those have transactional leadership. Besides, 92.7% of the respondents are in bachelor level, while only 1% in the master level.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The study is conducted to investigate “The Different Impact between Transformational Leadership and Transactional Leadership on Competitive Advantage” with a sample of 82 companies in Surabaya. The data is collected through questionnaire and the collected data is analyzed through computer software PLS. Empirical data were collected by way of a quantitative survey of 410 respondent. Respondents are asked to respond to specific likert-type scale items regarding the transformational leadership, transactional leadership, and competitive advantage.

Transformational Leadership is measured using adapted items from multifactor leadership questionnaire (MLQ) by [33]. Transactional Leadership is measured using adapted items from 5 item scale from component of transformational leadership by [34]. And competitive advantage is measured using adapted items from 5 item scale by [14].

Result

Reliability and Validity

Transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style and competitive advantages, as the latent variable, have good composite reliability scores (higher than 0.7), as well as the AVE scores that higher than 0.5.

The composite reliability of transformational leadership is 0.879 with AVE 0.592 and the composite reliability competitive advantage is 0.916 with AVE 0.527. And then, the composite reliability of transactional leadership and competitive advantage are 0.878 (transactional leadership) and 0.914 (competitive advantage). The transactional leadership AVE value is 0.646 and the competitive advantage AVE value is 0.522.

The validity measurement can be shown from loading factor coefficient of each indicator of latent variable. All indicators of the 3 latent variables are valid since the coefficient of its loading factors are higher than 0.5. All indicators of transformational leadership variable have high validity scores. The lowest score is on individualizes consideration, 0.720. Then, inspiration motivation (0.735), idealized influence-behavior (0.770), idealized influence-attributes (0.780) and the highest one is intellectual consideration, 0.836.

The same result also found in the transactional leadership variable. All indicators in this variable are valid based on the loading factor scores. The lowest score is personality compliments, 0.678. Then, special recognition (0.749), positive feedback (0.866) and the highest loading factor score is Commends, 0.902.

The indicators of competitive advantages are also valid. The loading factor score of price namely competitive price (0.902) and lower price (0.866). The loading factor score of quality namely highly reliable (0.678) and very durable (0.749). The loading factor score of delivery dependability namely deliver on time (0.699) and dependable delivery (0.770). The loading factor score of product innovation namely customized product (0.636) and meet client need (0.841). The loading factor score of time to market namely first in the market (0.656) and lower time to market (0.723). The result shows that the lowest loading factor score is Customized Product, 0.636; while the highest one is Competitive Price, 0.902.

The Impact of Transactional Leadership on Competitive Advantage

There is strong relationship between transformational leadership and competitive advantage. The t-statistic of the coefficient path ($t=55.483$) showed that transformational leadership has positive and significant influence towards competitive advantages. This result similar with [8], who implied that leader, is the strong determined factor in the developing of competitive advantages. The best achievement of competitive advantages is determined by employees [32], while the transformational leadership style is the leadership style that prioritize the improvement of employees' competencies that will automatically affect to the organization's competitive advantages. Thus H1 is accepted.

The result showed that Transformational leadership is disposed choose quality ($R^2=0.734$) and product innovation ($R^2=0.726$) as the way to develop the competitive advantages, as shown in this Table 2.

Table 2. The Impact of Transformational Leadership Style on the component of Competitive Advantage

influence	original sample estimate	standard deviation	T-statistic	R^2
Transformational to Price	0.736	0.018	40.561	0.541
Transactional to Quality	0.857	0.017	49.832	0.734
Transformational to Delivery	0.795	0.026	21.843	0.633
Transformational to Innovation	0.852	0.008	113.112	0.726
Transformational to Time to Market	0.832	0.014	60.106	0.692

This result of this research in line with the thinking of [30] who implied that transformational leader used intellectual stimulation (highest loading factor score 0.836) to encourage the employees to be creative and focus on the continuous improvement. Even, [35] emphasizes intellectual stimulation characteristic empower the employees to improve quality [4] also implied that transformational leader able to support the employees to be more intelligent. The creativity of the employees in the term of new ideas can be implemented in the creation of new products and new how. It is the proof that company always want to improve its competitive advantages towards product innovation and quality [14]. The leadership style of Steve Job in developing apple's product and focus on the quality is an example of transformational leadership.

Charismatic leadership, which is shown from the attributes and behavior, is also a good characteristic in describing transformational leadership style in the developing of competitive advantages. Similar to [29], this research also found that charismatic-attributes (the loading factor is 0.780) and charismatic-behavior (the loading factor is 0.770) are describing that transformational leadership is ethical. Charismatic leadership is a character that enable transformational leader to drive the employees to prioritize the organization more than their own interests [31]. Thus, it will facilitate the leader in motivating the employees to achieve the competitive advantages toward quality and product innovation.

The Impact of Transactional Leadership on Competitive Advantage

The path coefficient result ($t=165.245$), indicated that the influence of transactional leadership style in developing the competitive advantages, is very strong. This is similar to [8] who found that transactional leadership style has influence in the developing of competitive advantages. Thus H2 is accepted.

This research found that the character of giving commends to the high performance employees is the strongest character in transactional leadership style to develop the competitive advantages. The transactional leaders choose delivery dependability ($R^2=0.866$) and time to market ($R^2=0.8333$) as the best ways in developing the competitive advantages, as shown in this Table 3.

Table 3. The Impact of Transactional Leadership Style on the component of Competitive Advantage

influence	original sample estimate	standard deviation	T-statistic	F _t
Transactional to Price	0.843	0.012	70.949	0.711
Transactional to Quality	0.829	0.015	56.799	0.687
Transactional to Delivery	0.898	0.008	109.568	0.866
Transactional to Innovation	0.786	0.045	17.579	0.618
Transactional to Time to Market	0.913	0.007	122.289	0.833

Transactional leaders encourage the employees to be the number one in the market in the form of speed and accuracy of meet the customers' expectations. From the high score of path coefficient, the result in this research is in line with the opinion of [7] who implied that transactional leaders are disposed to encourage the employees to behave positively with the leaders' expectation. The reason behind the positive behavior is their expectation to get more rewards (contingent reward) from their leaders. The commend-reward to the employees when they can achieve high performance can motivate the employees to produce a masterwork for the organization. The speed and accuracy in responding the market needs is the standard for the employees to get the rewards from their leaders. The employees who are motivated to be the best in their performance will automatically increase organization performance beyond the competitors; therefore the organization can win the market. Positive feedback is also a reward that can encourage the employee to behave positively in the organization [7]. Therefore, the more transactional leaders deliver positive feedback to the high performance employees (the loading factor is 0.866), it will also motivate them to be the number one in the market.

This research support by [4] who implied that the transactional leadership style has strongest influence in developing companies' competitive advantages in Surabaya. This shows that the employees in Surabaya are disposed to emphasize on the important of trade-off between organization's interests with their own interests. Thus, transactional leadership style is properly applied in facing the business competitiveness in Surabaya. This result also supported by [7] who implied that transactional leadership has strong influence in developing the competitive advantages by pushing the employees to perform well with the reward and punishment system.

Predictive Model of Leadership Style and Competitive Advantage

The research model is dependable, as it is stated picture 2. GOF Measurement which is seen from coefficient $Q^2 = R^2 = 0.816$ for transformational leadership dan $Q^2 = R^2 = 0.897$ for transactional leadership which is closest to number 1 indicate that this research model can predict accurately.

Picture 2. The Model of the Different Impact of Leadership Style on Competitive Advantage

Conclusion

The role of leadership style is very strong in developing competitive advantages. Intellectual stimulation is the strongest characteristic of transformational leadership in developing the competitive advantages; and giving commands is the strongest characteristic of transactional leadership. Apparently, this research found that in Surabaya, transactional leadership has strongest influence than transformational leadership. The process of developing company's competitive advantages is also highly influenced by the leadership style. Transactional leaders prefer to have delivery dependability and time to market as the factors for their outstanding performance. Transformational leaders prefer to have quality and product innovation as the best factors to develop the organization's competitive advantages. The result of this research should be continued by having another broader research out of Surabaya City so it can be done as the basic to develop leadership style to achieve competitive advantage.

References

- [1] Hitt, M. A., Keats, B. A., and DeMarie, S. M., Navigating in the new competitive landscape: Building strategic flexibility and competitive advantage in the 21st century, *Academy of Management Executive*, 12, 1998, pp. 22–42.
- [2] Porter, M.E., Improving Indonesia's Competitiveness, 2009, http://www.slideshare.net/Joe_2009/improving-indonesia-competitiveness.
- [3] Alak. A.A. and Tarabieh, S.A., Gaining competitive advantage and organizational performance through customer orientation, innovation differentiation and market differentiation, *International Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 1(5), 2003, pp. 80-91.
- [4] Khan, S. and Anjum, M.A., Role of Leadership Style and Its Impact on Getting Competitive Advantage, *European Journal of Applied Sciences*, 5, 2013, pp. 53-61.
- [5] Bass, B., *Transformational leadership: Industry, military, and educational impact*, Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum Associates, 1998.
- [6] Ehrhardt, M.G. and Klein, K.J., Predicting followers' preferences for charismatic leadership: The influence of follower values and personality, *The Leadership Quarterly*, 12, 2001, pp. 153-179.
- [7] Timothy, O. C., Okwu, A. T., Akpa, V. A. O., and Nwankwere, I., Effects of Leadership Style Organizational Performance: A Survey of Selected Small Scale Enterprises In Ikosi-Ketu Council Development Area of Lagos State, Nigeria, *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research* (1), 2011.
- [8] Agbor, E., Creativity and innovation: The leadership dynamic, *Journal of Strategic Leadership*, 1(1), 2008, 39-45.
- [9] Barney, J., Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage, *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 1991, 99-120.
- [10] D'Souza, D. E. and Williams, F. P., Toward a taxonomy of manufacturing flexibility dimensions, *Journal of Operations Management*, 18, 2000, pp. 577-583.
- [11] Grant, R. M., Porter's 'Competitive Advantage of Nations': An Assessment Strategic, *Management Journal*, 12(7), 1991, ABI/INFORM Global, 535.
- [12] Lie. J.J. and Zou. K.Z., How foreign firms achieve competitive advantage in the Chinese emerging economy: Managerial ties and market orientation, *Journal of Business Research*, 63, 2010, pp. 856–862.
- [13] Porter, M. E., *Towards A dynamic Theory of Strategy*, *Strategic Management Journal*, John Willey & Sons, Ltd. 1991).
- [14] Li, S., Ragu-Nathan, B., Ragu-Nathan, T. S., and Rao, S. S., The Impact of Supply Chain Management Practices on Competitive Advantage and Organizational Performance, *Omega*, 34, 2006, pp. 107-124.
- [15] Antonakis, J., Avolio, B.J., and Sivasubramaniam, N., Context and leadership: an examination of the nine-factor full-range leadership theory using the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire, *Leadership Quarterly*, 14, 2003, pp. 261-295.
- [16] Paracha, M. U., Qamar, A., Mirza, A. H., Inam-Ul, and Hamid, W., Impact of Leadership Style (Transformational & Transactional Leadership) On Employee Performance & Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction? Study of Private School (Educator) In Pakistan, *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 12(4), 2012.
- [17] Bass, B.M., Avolio, B.J., Jung, D.I., and Berson, Y., Predicting unit performance by assessing transformational and transactional leadership, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(2), 2003, pp. 207-218.
- [18] Bass, B. M., The Future of Leadership in Learning Organizations, *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 7(3), 2000, pp. 18-40.
- [19] Ojokuku, R. M., Odateyo, T. A., and Sajuyigbe, A. S., Impact of Leadership Style on Organizational Performance: A Case Study of Nigerian Banks, *American Journal of Business and Management*, 1(4), 2012, pp. 202-207.

- [20] Yun, S., Cox, J., Sims, H. P., and Salam, S., Leadership and Teamwork: The Effects of Leadership and Job Satisfaction on Team Citizenship, *International Journal of Leadership Studies*, 2(3), 2007, pp. 171-193.
- [21] Lo, M. C., Ramayah, T., and Min, H. W., Leadership styles and organizational commitment: a test on Malaysia manufacturing industry, *African Journal of Marketing Management*, 1(6), 2009, pp. 133-139.
- [22] Janssen, O. and Yperen, N. W., Employees' goal orientations, the quality of Leader-member exchange, and the outcomes of job Performance and job satisfaction, *Academy of Management Journal*, 47(3), 2004, pp. 368-384.
- [23] Hamilton, M., The Interaction of Transactional and Transformational Leadership, *Online Journal of Workforce Education and Development*, 3(3), 2010.
- [24] Nikezic, S., Puric, S., and Puric, J., Transactional and Transformational Leadership: Development Through Changes, *International Journal for Quality research*, 6(3), 2012.
- [25] Bass, B.M., Does the Transactional - Transformational Leadership Paradigm Transcend Organizational and National Boundaries?. *American Psychologist*, 52(2), 1997, pp. 130-139.
- [26] Jeremy, M., Melinde, C., and Cilliers, V., Perceived leadership style and employee participation in a manufacturing company in the democratic republic of Congo, *African Journal of Business Management*, 6(15), 2012, pp. 5389-5398.
- [27] Hambley, L., Neill, T., and Kline, T., Virtual team leadership: The effects of leadership style and communication medium on team interaction styles and outcomes, *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 103, 2007, pp. 1-20.
- [28] Tracey, Michael, Vonderembse, Mark, A., and Lim, Jeen-Su., Manufacturing Technology and Strategy Formulation: Keys to Enhancing Competitiveness and Improving Performance. *Journal of Operation Management*, 17, 1999.
- [29] Proctor, T. S. B. and Parry, K., Perceived Integrity of Transformational Leaders in Organisational Setting, *Journal of Business Ethics*, 35(2), 2002.
- [30] Sarros, J. C. and Santora, J. C., The Transformational-Transactional Leadership Model in Practice, *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 22(7/8), 2001.
- [31] Bass, B.M., Two Decades of Research and Development in Transformational Leadership, *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 8(1), 1999, pp. 9-32.
- [32] Dvir, T., Eden, D., Avolio, B.J., and Shamir, B., Impact of Transformational Leadership on Follower Development and Performance: A Field Experiment. In Press—AMJ, Faculty of Management Tel Aviv University Ramat Aviv, Tel Aviv 69978, Israel, 2002.
- [33] Avolio, B.J. and Bass, B.M., *MLQ Manual*. Mind Garden Inc. 2004.
- [34] Men, L.R., Measuring the impact of leadership style and employee empowerment on perceived organization reputation. University of Miami, Submitted to the Institute of Public Relations, 2010.
- [35] Bartram, T. and Casimir, G., The Relationship between leadership and follower in-role performance and satisfaction with the leader, *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 28, 2007.